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ИЗУЧЕНИЕ НЕЙРОПРОТЕКТИВНЫХ СВОЙСТВ И НЕЙРОРЕАБИТОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ РОЛИ ШАФРАНА В ЛЕЧЕНИИ ЭПИЛЕПТИЧЕСКИХ ПРИСТУПОВ

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STUDY OF THE NEUROPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES AND NEUROREABITOLOGICAL ROLE OF SAFFRON IN THE MANAGEMENT OF EPILEPTIC SEIZURES

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Аннотация

Эпилепсия является наиболее распространенным, внезапным и неконтролируемым неврологическим заболеванием в мире, обусловленным различными причинами. Хотя причину ее возникновения во время заболевания точно определить невозможно – она может быть вызвана родовыми травмами, опухолями, воспалением головного мозга и т. д. Это заболевание может появиться в разном возрасте, начиная с детского возраста. Во время эпилепсии происходит внезапная и неконтролируемая разрядка нейронов в соответствующих долях головного мозга. Кроме того, височные доли являются областью мозга, вызывающей наибольшее количество судорог. В настоящее время причины и методы исследования эпилепсии не полностью доступны, поэтому исследование темы создает основу для ее актуальности. На модели миндалевидной эпилепсии в ходе экспериментов определяли нейрореабилитационный эффект шафрана, снижение окислительного стресса такие его свойства, как регуляция эпилептических припадков. Нейропротекторное свойство шафрана наблюдалось в уменьшении продолжительности эпилепсии и ослаблении синхронных припадков. Таким образом, на основе наших экспериментов выяснилось, что шафран обладает полезным свойством при эпилепсии в модели миндалевидного эпилептогенеза, пенициллин.

Abstract

Epilepsy is the most widespread, sudden and uncontrolled neurological disease in the world due to various reasons. Although the cause of its occurrence during the disease cannot be determined precisely - it can be caused by birth traumas, tumors, brain inflammation, etc. This disease can appear at different ages, starting from childhood. During epilepsy, there is a sudden and uncontrolled discharge of neurons in the corresponding lobes of the brain. Also, the temporal lobes are the region of the brain that causes the most seizures. Currently, the cause and examination of epilepsy is not fully available, so researching the topic creates the basis for its relevance. The neurorehabilitation effect of saffron in the amygdalar epilepsy model, its properties such as regulation of epileptic seizures and reduction of oxidative stress were determined during experiments. The neuroprotective property of saffron has been observed in reducing the duration of epilepsy and weakening of synchronous seizures. Thus, based on our experiments, it was learned that saffron has a beneficial property during epiactivity in the amygdalar epileptogenesis model.

Ключевые слова: миндалевидная эпилепсия, шафран, судороги, окислительный стресс, нейродегенеративная дисфункция.

Keywords: amygdalar epilepsy, saffron, seizure, oxidative stress, neurodegenerative dysfunction, penicillin.

A number of diseases are caused by the disruption of neuronal functions in the body. Epilepsy is one of the most widespread of these diseases. Epilepsy is a chronic non-infectious disease of the brain that affects people of all ages. The cause of epilepsy is among the diseases that are not completely clear. For example, brain damage due to prenatal or perinatal reasons (for example, oxygen loss or trauma during birth, low birth weight); genetic conditions associated with congenital abnormalities or associated brain defects; severe head injury; a stroke that limits the amount of oxygen to the brain; brain infection such as meningitis, encephalitis or neurocysticercosis, certain genetic syndromes; and

brain tumor.³ About 50 million people worldwide suffer from epilepsy, making it one of the most common neurological diseases in the world. About 80% of people with epilepsy live in low- and middle-income countries. (Guerreiro, 2016), (World Health Organization, 2024). It is estimated that up to 70% of people living with epilepsy can live without seizures if properly diagnosed and treated. People with epilepsy are up to three times more likely to die prematurely than the general population. Three-quarters of epilepsy patients in low-income countries do not receive adequate treatment. In many parts of the world, people with epilepsy and their families suffer from stigma and discrimination (WHO, 2024). Epilepsy is a brain disease caused by

repeated seizures for which the cause is not fully understood. The frequency of neurodegenerative dysfunctions in epilepsy can occur at different ages, as a tendency to repeated seizures for different reasons. (Neri, Mastroianni, Gardella, Aguglia and Rubboli, (2022). Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disease characterized by recurrent seizures (Guerreiro,2016).

Thus, epilepsy, as one of the most common neurological diseases, affects people of all ages, races, social classes, and geographic locations. Epilepsy is a brain disease characterized by a persistent tendency to seizures and the neurobiological, cognitive (cognitive, thinking), psychological and social consequences of repeated seizures. Epileptic seizures are recurrent paroxysmal events characterized by stereotyped behavioral changes that reflect the underlying neural mechanisms of the disease. The differential diagnosis of epilepsy includes a number of clinical conditions characterized by temporary changes in consciousness or behavior. In most cases, the disease can be diagnosed with a careful history or seizure observation. Although the etiological agent has been identified, the cause is still unknown in about half of the cases. A variable genetic predisposition to the manifestation of seizures and a different distribution of some environmental risk factors may explain the heterogeneity of the incidence, course, and outcome of the disease worldwide. In addition to seizure recurrence, the underlying cause and adverse effects of treatment have neurological, cognitive, psychological, and social consequences that significantly affect the quality of life of affected individuals, making the disease a complex nosographic entity (Liu, MD, Slater, PharmD, and Perkins,2017).

As a result of research, it was determined that the injection of penicillin solution into the amygdala of animals led to the development of long-lasting convulsive activity. After 1 minute, individual epileptiform discharges appear in the EEG of all studied structures. Changes in the activity of brain structures begin to synchronize during experimental epileptogenesis. Activity that begins in the amygdala begins to spread to visual structures and the retina. As a result, the activity was maintained in animals for 3-4 hours. Within an hour, convulsions reach their peak, after which certain dynamics of epileptiform waves are formed. Thus, over time, the attacks begin to replace each other. 2.5 hours after the injection of penicillin into the amygdala, the number of alternate epileptic seizures begins to decrease and the activity stops. EEG registration of several brain structures allows determining the temporal sequence of the connection of the studied structures with the pathological process. It has been established that epileptic activity originates first in the amygdala, then in the visual cortex, superior colliculus and external geniculate body, and also affects the activity of the retina. Referring to literature sources, we know that there are methods of treating epilepsy or shortening its duration. But more experiments are needed for this. Studying the mechanisms of the processes occurring in the visual system in the model of amygdalar epilepsy allows us to understand its pathogenesis. Some information was obtained during the study of the effect of

natural antioxidant saffron in his rehabilitation. Determining the effectiveness of herbal medicines in the treatment of diseases is the basis of experiments conducted by physiologists in the field of medicine. The results of the conducted experimental experiments show that the therapeutic effects of saffron and its constituents, crocin, crocetin and safranal, were mainly manifested by preventing inflammatory reactions and treating epilepsy, which is a neurodegenerative disease, both as a food and as an extract.

Crocus sativus (saffron) is traditionally used to cure a number of ailments. Experimental studies have also investigated the application of saffron and its active components in the treatment of a wide range of diseases. A growing body of evidence has shown the value of saffron and its components alone or in combination with other drugs to improve learning and memory abilities and to control seizures. These findings may provide a pharmacological basis for the use of saffron in cognitive disorders and epilepsy. However, further pre-clinical and clinical studies are needed. Together, these findings indicate the pharmacological basis for the use of saffron in the treatment and prevention of neurodegenerative diseases. (Rajabian, Hosseini, Hosseini, Sadeghnia, 2019). Therefore, we started experiments in several directions to investigate the effect of saffron on epilepsy. Our main goal was to reduce or stop epileptic symptoms.

Recent studies have suggested that safranal has anticonvulsant properties. All these advantages have been obtained along with the studies conducted and the valuable information about safranal's protective effect against convulsions. Further studies are also needed to elucidate the exact mechanism and potential ability of safranal to prevent flares, as well as to establish clinical implications for the treatment of epileptic disorders (Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2022). In order to study the neuroprotective and anticonvulsant properties of saffron, we performed a direct injection of its extract into the brain, which we prepared in advance using a special method. The studies were conducted on male gray rabbits of the "Chinchilla" breed. Rabbits were divided into two groups: group I rabbits were fed only vegetables, and group II rabbits were given saffron in a predetermined dose and at the same time along with vegetables. Epilepsy was induced in both groups of rabbits. As a result, the duration of epilepsy in rabbits fed with saffron was shortened, and short-amplitude waves prevailed over high-amplitude waves. Very few epileptic seizures or morphological clinical signs were observed in rabbits during the experiment. Based on the results, it can be said that the saffron extract reduced the oxidative stress in the brain during epilepsy, significantly reduced the duration of the seizures and morphological clinical indicators, and helped the animal to return to its normal state. Thus, in these experiments, we determined that saffron is not a treatment goal, but an antioxidant that increases tolerance to epilepsy. One of the biggest goals ahead is to reveal its therapeutic effect in our next experiments. (Rajabian et., 2019).

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